

Effects of Physical Activity on Wellbeing among Children with ADHD: A Mediation by Self-Esteem

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Received: 18 June 2022

Accepted: 14 August 2022

Published: 06 September 2022

Abstract

It has been shown that physical activity positively affects wellbeing of children and adolescents. However, this issue has rarely been investigated among special groups such as ADHD. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of physical activity level on physical and psychological wellbeing of children with ADHD with the mediating role of self-esteem.

Children aged 9 to 11 years old attended in special school for children with ADHD participated in this study. Physical activity, wellbeing, and self-esteem were measured by using standard questionnaires. Structural equation modelling was used to analyze data.

On average, level of children' physical activity, wellbeing, and self-esteem were lower than the average. Physical activity positively affected physical and psychological wellbeing as well as self-esteem among children with ADHD. Moreover, self-esteem can be considered as a plausible mechanism for the relationship between physical activity and wellbeing.

These findings, together, indicate that physical activity and wellbeing are critical concerns for children with ADHD. Accordingly, it is necessary to adopt appropriate strategies to increase the level of physical activity among children with ADHD.

Keywords: ADHD, physical activity, wellbeing, self-esteem.

How to cite the article:

F. Shafaeian Fard, T. Baniasadi, T. Soltan Ahmadi, P. Biyabani, S. Khajeaflaton Mofrad, *Effects of Physical Activity on Wellbeing among Children with ADHD: A Mediation by Self-Esteem*, *J. Hum. Ins.* 2022; 6(3): 01-06. DOI: 10.22034/JHI.2022.330605.1056

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1. Introduction

Physical activity is defined as any voluntary bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure (World Health Organization, 2020). It has been shown that regular physical activity has immediate and long-term health benefits. It can improve health and reduce the risk of chronic diseases such as type 2 diabetes, cancer and cardiovascular disease. In addition,

regular physical activity can improve mental health and quality of life (Basterfield et al. 2021; Lahart et al. 2019; Schwartz et al. 2019; Tremblay et al. 2011; Wafa et al. 2016; Zhang et al. 2021). Thus, to maintain health and reduce risk of health problems, World Health Organization's (WHO) recommends that all people should engage in at least 60 minutes of daily moderate-to-vigorous-intensity (MVPA) physical activity across the week (World Health

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Organization, 2020). However, it has been consistently demonstrated that a small number of children and adolescents (20-25 percent of girls and 35-40 percent of boys) engage for at least in 60 minutes of daily MVPA (Sallis et al. 2016; Hosseini et al. 2020; Gholidahaneh et al. 2020; Ghorbani et al. 2021). This can be more acute among particular groups such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), a common neurodevelopment disorders among children that can persist into adolescence and adulthood. ADHD is associated with an ongoing pattern of inattention, hyperactivity, and/or impulsivity. Symptoms of ADHD can interfere with daily activities and relationships. It is also associated with a high rate of psychiatric problems such as mood and anxiety disorders, and cigarette and substance use disorders (Birchwood et al. 2012; Goulardins et al. 2017). It has been shown that children and adolescents with ADHD do not follow WHO recommendation of 60 minutes of daily MVPA (Gallego-Méndez et al. 2020; Li et al. 2021), and subsequently experience inactivity and its negative consequences. Thus, physical activity is an important topic in the field of children and adolescents with ADHD.

Moreover, some studies have shown that physical activity can improve the wellbeing of children and adolescents (Breslin et al. 2017). However, this issue has been less studied in children and adolescents with ADHD. Wellbeing is a person's ability to recognize their own capacities, manage regular stresses of life, work productively, and contribute to their community. Wellbeing is not just the absence of disease or illness. It's a complex combination of a person's physical, mental, emotional and social health factors. Wellbeing is strongly linked to happiness and life satisfaction. In short, wellbeing could be described as how person feels about himself and his life (Sfeatcu et al. 2014). Thus, wellbeing can be considered as a vital factor in life, especially among people with physical and mental disabilities. As mentioned earlier, associations between physical activity and wellbeing among children with ADHD has been rarely investigated. Therefore, the first aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of physical activity level on physical and psychological wellbeing of children with ADHD.

In addition, it has been shown that every aspect of life influences the state of wellbeing. Some studies have shown that self-esteem enhances a person's wellbeing. In psychology, the term self-esteem is used to describe a person's overall subjective sense of personal worth or value. In other words, self-esteem may be defined as how much a person appreciates and like himself regardless of the circumstances (Kim et al. 2021; Haugen et al. 2013). However, its effects on wellbeing of children and

adolescents with ADHD has been rarely examined. Thus, the second aim of this study was to investigate the mediating role of self-esteem in the relationships between physical activity and wellbeing among children with ADHD. Altogether, this study aimed to evaluate the effects of physical activity level on physical and psychological wellbeing of children with ADHD with the mediating role of self-esteem.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

The method used in this study was descriptive-correlation. 119 children aged 9 to 11 years old attended in special school for children with ADHD participated in this study who were selected based on convenience sampling method.

2.2 Measures

2.2.1 Physical activity: We applied Physical Activity Behavior in Leisure-Time Scale to measure leisure-time physical activity of children with ADHD (Dana et al. 2021). This questionnaire contains three questions scored based on an eight-point Likert scale from zero days (0) to seven days (7). In the current study, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.90.

2.2.2 Wellbeing: Well-being (i.e., physical and psychological aspects) was measured using the 7-day recall Kidscreen-27 questionnaire (McDowell, 2009). Physical well-being was assessed using 5 items regarding children's perceptions of their physical activity, health and vitality. It includes items that refer to the children's energy and their ability to physically function. Psychological well-being was assessed using 7 items exploring children's experiences of positive and negative affect. Items are worded to reflect the children's mood, enjoyment and experiences of happiness and loneliness (24). All items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = never, 2 = seldom, 3 = quite often, 4 = very often and 5 = always which reflecting the frequency of behaviors or feelings; or 1 = not at all, 2 = slightly, 3 = moderately, 4 = very, 5 = extremely which reflecting the intensity of a belief or attitude in the previous week (24). In this study, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.89.

2.2.3 Self-Esteem: We used The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg, 1965) to measure the children' self-esteem. This instrument includes 10 four-point Likert items from strongly disagree (0) to strongly agree (3). In this study, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.90.

2.3 Data analysis

Data was analyzed by SPSS-26 and Lisrel software. Descriptive statistics including means and standard deviations were used to describe the variables. Spearman correlation test was used to evaluate the

associations between variables. Structural equation method was used to examine the effects of physical activity on wellbeing with mediation of self-esteem. P-value was set at $P < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1 Demographic data

Descriptive data is presented in Table 1. In general, the level of children' physical activity, wellbeing, and self-esteem were lower than the average.

Table 1. Mean and SDs of research variables

	Physical Activity	Physical Wellbeing	Psychological Wellbeing	Self-Esteem
Mean	1.42	1.66	1.93	10.81
SD	0.66	0.71	0.80	5.17

3.2 Associations among research variables

Table 2 represents bivariate relationships between research variables. Results showed significant direct relationship between: 1) physical activity and physical wellbeing ($P < 0.001$), 2) physical

activity and psychological wellbeing ($P < 0.001$), 3) physical activity and self-esteem ($P < 0.001$), 4) self-esteem and physical wellbeing ($P < 0.001$), and 5) self-esteem and psychological wellbeing ($P < 0.001$).

Table 2. Results of bivariate relationships between variables

	1	2	3	4
1. Physical Activity	-			
2. Physical Wellbeing	r=0.408 P<0.001	-		
3. Psychological Wellbeing	r=0.619 P<0.001	r=0.341 P<0.001	-	
4. Self-Esteem	r=0.550 P<0.001	r=0.806 P<0.001	r=0.778 P<0.001	-

3.3 Structural Equation Modelling

The results of structural equation modelling are presented in Table 3 and Figure 1. Results were as following: 1) physical activity positively affected physical wellbeing ($T=5.569$), 2) physical activity positively affected psychological wellbeing ($T=9.017$), 3) physical activity positively affected self-esteem ($T=7.173$), 4) self-esteem positively affected physical wellbeing ($T=8.528$), and 5) self-

esteem positively affected psychological wellbeing ($T=7.980$), and 6) self-esteem has significantly mediated the relationship between physical activity and physical and psychological wellbeing (both $P < 0.001$). Table 4 represents the results of model fit. The results indicate that good fit for research model.

Table 3. Results of structural equation modelling

	Path	β	T-value
1	Physical Activity => Physical Wellbeing	0.340	5.569
2	Physical Activity => Psychological Wellbeing	0.567	9.017
3	Physical Activity => Self-Esteem	0.409	7.173
4	Self-Esteem => Physical Wellbeing	0.507	8.528
5	Self-Esteem => Psychological Wellbeing	0.493	7.980
		Z	P-value
6	Physical Activity => Self-Esteem => Physical Wellbeing	5.882	P<0.001
7	Physical Activity => Self-Esteem => Psychological Wellbeing	4.937	P<0.001

Figure 1. Structural equation modelling in the form of T-values

Table 4. Results of model fit

Index	Optimal Range	Obtained Value	Conclusion
RMSEA	< 0.08	0.05	Good fit
χ^2 / df	< 3	2.80	Good fit
RMR	Closer to 0	0.02	Good fit
NFI	> 0.9	0.98	Good fit
CFI	> 0.9	0.92	Good fit

4. Discussion

It has been shown that physical activity positively affects wellbeing of children and adolescents. (Dana et al. 2021; Calzada-Rodríguez et al. 2021). However, this issue has rarely been investigated among special groups such as ADHD. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of physical activity level on physical and psychological wellbeing of children with ADHD with the mediating role of self-esteem. Results of descriptive statistics showed that the level of children' physical activity, wellbeing, and self-esteem were lower than the average. This low level is quite understandable, because of their difficulties with motor and cognitive functions. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt appropriate strategies to improve the physical activity, as well as perception of wellbeing and self-esteem among children with ADHD. Regarding structural equation modelling, the results showed that physical activity positively affected physical and psychological wellbeing as well as self-esteem among children with ADHD. The present findings are in accordance with those of previous studies (Basterfield et al. 2021; Lahart et al. 2019; Schwartz et al. 2019; Tremblay et al. 2011; Wafa et al. 2016; Zhang et al. 2021), indicating positive role of physical activity in improving wellbeing of children with ADHD. Several plausible mechanisms may explain the observed association between higher levels of physical activity and better

reported wellbeing among children with ADHD including increases in neurogenesis and reductions in inflammatory and oxidant markers as well as improvements in self-esteem (Schuch et al. 2016, 2018; Zamani Sani et al. 2016). In fact, as mentioned earlier, self-esteem can play an important mediating role in the relationship between physical activity and wellbeing. Thus, it can be considered as a possible mechanism in this relationship.

Among limitations of the present study, due to the fact that we used questionnaire to assess levels of physical activity of children with ADHD, it has self-reporting bias (Slootmaker et al. 2009). Moreover, among limitations of the present study, we made use of a relatively small sample size. Further research with higher amount of sample size is needed to increase the reliability of data.

To conclude, this cross-sectional study revealed children with ADHD engage in few amounts of physical activity as well as have low wellbeing and self-esteem. However, physical activity was associated with higher wellbeing and self-esteem. Moreover, self-esteem can be considered as a plausible mechanism for the relationship between physical activity and wellbeing. These findings, together, indicate that physical activity and wellbeing are critical concerns for children with ADHD. Accordingly, it is necessary to adopt appropriate strategies to increase the level of physical activity among children with ADHD.

References

1. Basterfield L, Burn NL, Galna B, Karoblyte G, Weston KL. The association between physical fitness, sports club participation and body mass index on health-related quality of life in primary school children from a socioeconomically deprived area of England. *Prev Med Rep.* 2021;24:101557.
2. Birchwood J, Daley D. Brief report: the impact of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) symptoms on academic performance in an adolescent community sample. *J Adol.* 2012;35(1):225-231.
3. Breslin, G., Fitzpatrick, B., Brennan, D., Shannon, S., Rafferty, R., O'Brien, W., Belton, S., Chambers, F., Haughey, T., McCullagh, D., Gormley, R., & Hanna, D. (2017). Physical activity and wellbeing of 8–9 year old children from social disadvantage: An all-Ireland approach to health. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 13, 9-14.
4. Calzada-Rodríguez JI, et al. Health-Related Quality of Life and Frequency of Physical Activity in Spanish Students Aged 8-14. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021;18:9418.
5. Dana A, Khajehafaton S, Salehian M, Sarvari S. Effects of an Intervention in Online Physical Education Classes on Motivation, Intention, and Physical Activity of Adolescents during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Int J School Health.* 2021;8(3):141-149.
6. Dana A, Nodeh H, Salehian M, Mokari Saei S, Sarvari S. Smartphone Usage Status, Sleep Pattern, Health-Related Quality of Life, and Physical Activity among Adolescents from before to during the COVID-19 Confinement: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Int J School Health.* 2021.
7. Gallego-Méndez J, Perez-Gomez J, Calzada-Rodríguez JI, Denche-Zamorano AM, Mendoza-Muñoz M, Carlos-Vivas J, Garcia-Gordillo MÁ, Adsuar JC. Relationship between Health-Related Quality of Life and Physical Activity in Children with Hyperactivity. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(8):2804.
8. Gholidahaneh MG, Ghorbani S, Esfahaninia A. Effects of Basic Psychological Needs Satisfaction in the Physical Education on Leisure-Time Physical Activity Behavior of Primary School Students: Mediating Role of Autonomous Motivation. *Int J Sch Health.* 2020;7(2):46-53.
9. Ghorbani S, Afshari M, Eckelt M, Dana A, Bund A. Associations between Physical Activity and Mental Health in Iranian Adolescents during the COVID-19 Pandemic: An Accelerometer-Based Study. *Children.* 2021;8(11):1022.
10. Goulardins JB, Marques JCB, DeOliveira JA. Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder and Motor Impairment: A Critical Review. *Percept Mot Skills.* 2017;124(2):425-40.
11. Haugen T, Ommundsen Y, Seiler S. The Relationship Between Physical Activity and Physical Self-Esteem in Adolescents: The Role of Physical Fitness Indices, *Ped Exer Sci.* 2013.25(1):138-153.
12. Hosseini FB, Ghorbani S, Rezaeshirazi R. Effects of Perceived Autonomy Support in the Physical Education on Basic Psychological Needs Satisfaction, Intrinsic Motivation and Intention to Physical Activity in High-School Students. *Int J School Health.* 2020;7(4), 39-46.
13. Kim, I.; Ahn, J. The Effect of Changes in Physical Self-Concept through Participation in Exercise on Changes in Self-Esteem and Mental Well-Being. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2021, 18, 5224. Doi:10.3390/ijerph18105224.
14. Lahart I, Darcy P, Gidlow C, Calogiuri G. The Effects of Green Exercise on Physical and Mental Wellbeing: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2019;16(8):1352.
15. Li R, Liang X, Liu F, Zhou Z, Zhang Z, Lu Y, Wang P, Yang B. Mediating Effect of Motor Competence on the Relationship between Physical Activity and Quality of Life in Children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder. *Biomed Res Int.* 2021;24:4814250.
16. McDowell, I. (2009). Measures of self-perceived well-being. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 69(1), 69-79.
17. Sallis JF, et al. Progress in physical activity over the Olympic quadrennium. *Lancet.* 2016;388:1325-1336.
18. Rosenberg M. *Society and the Adolescent Self-Image.* Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press. 1965.
19. Schuch FB, Deslandes AC, Stubbs B, Gosmann NP, Silva CT, Fleck MP. Neurobiological effects of exercise on major depressive disorder: A systematic review. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2016 Feb;61:1-11. doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2015.11.012. Epub 2015 Dec 2. PMID: 26657969.
20. Schuch FB, Vancampfort D, Firth J, Rosenbaum S, Ward PB, Silva ES, Hallgren M, Ponce De Leon A, Dunn AL, Deslandes AC, Fleck MP, Carvalho AF, Stubbs B. Physical Activity and Incident Depression: A Meta-Analysis of Prospective Cohort Studies. *Am J Psychiatry.* 2018 Jul 1;175(7):631-648. doi: 10.1176/appi.ajp.2018.17111194. Epub 2018 Apr 25. PMID: 29690792.
21. Schwartz J, Rhodes R, Bredin S, Oh P, Warburton D. Effectiveness of Approaches to Increase Physical Activity Behavior to Prevent Chronic Disease in Adults: A Brief Commentary. *J Clin Med.* 2019;8(3):295.

22. Sfeatcu R, Cernuşcă-Miţariu M, Ionescu C, Roman M, Cernuşcă-Miţariu S, Coldea L, et al. The concept of well-being in relation to health and quality of life. *European Journal of Science and Theology*. 2014;10(4):123–8.
23. Slootmaker, S.M.; Schuit, A.J.; Chinapaw, M.J.; et al. Disagreement in physical activity assessed by accelerometer and self-report in subgroups of age, gender, education and weight status. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2009, 6, 17.
24. Tremblay MS, et al. Systematic review of sedentary behavior and health indicators in school-aged children and youth. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2011;8:98.
25. Wafa SW, Shahril MR, Ahmad AB, Zainuddin LR, Ismail KF, Aung MM, Mohd Yusoff NA. Association between physical activity and health-related quality of life in children: a cross-sectional study. *Health Qual Life Outcomes*. 2016;4:71.
26. World Health Organization. WHO guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. World Health Organization. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/336656>. License: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. 2020.
27. Zamani Sani SH, Fathirezaie Z, Brand S, Pühse U, Holsboer-Trachsler E, Gerber M, Talepasand S. Physical activity and self-esteem: testing direct and indirect relationships associated with psychological and physical mechanisms. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat*. 2016;12:2617-2625.
28. Zhang X, Tan SS, Franse CB, Alhambra-Borrás T, Verma A, Williams G, van Grieken A, Raat H. Longitudinal association between physical activity and health-related quality of life among community-dwelling older adults: a longitudinal study of Urban Health Centres Europe (UHCE). *BMC Geriatr*. 2021;21(1):52.